

Anterior Versus Posterior Iris Intraocular Lens Implantation for the Treatment of Aphakia without Sufficient Capsule Support: A Hospital Based Retrospective Study

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Abstract:

Background: Aphakia, the condition of having no lens in the eye, poses significant visual challenges and requires effective surgical intervention.

Objectives: To compare the long-term efficacy and the rate of complications of anterior and posterior Iris IOL implantation for the treatment of aphakia without sufficient capsule support.

Methods: This was a hospital based retrospective study conducted in the outpatient department and/or inpatient wards of the Department of Ophthalmology, in a tertiary teaching healthcare facility in North India between January 2021 and June 2024.

Results: The study involved 240 patients divided into two groups. The mean age for Group A was 68.1 years and 69.4 years for Group B ($p>0.05$). Gender distribution was similar, with Group A having 67 males (55.8%) and Group B having 69 males (57.5%). The involvement of right and left eyes was comparable between the groups, and the etiologies of aphakia showed no significant differences. Preoperative corrected distance visual acuity (CDVA) was 0.4 (logMAR) in both groups, improving significantly postoperatively to 0.1 by the third year. Preoperative intraocular pressure (IOP) was similar between the groups, with postoperative measurements showing an initial increase at one week, which normalized by the third year. Corneal endothelial cell density (CECD) decreased slightly over time in both groups, with no significant intergroup differences. Early complications (first week to third month) included wound leaks, hyphema, pupil ovalization, IOP elevation, pigment precipitates, and other complications, none of which differed significantly between the groups. Late complications (first to fifth year) such as elevated IOP, IOL dislocation, pigment precipitates, and retinal tear/detachment were also not significantly different between the groups.

Conclusion: Anterior and posterior iris-claw IOL implantations showed comparable efficacy and safety profiles, with no significant differences in visual outcomes, IOP, CECD, or complication rates between the two techniques.

Keywords: Aphakia, Iris Intraocular lens, Corrected distance visual acuity, intraocular pressure, corneal endothelial cell density, India.

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Introduction

Aphakia, the condition of having no lens in the eye, poses significant visual challenges and requires effective surgical intervention. This condition often arises due to traumatic injury, complicated cataract surgery, or spontaneous lens dislocation, where the natural lens is either lost or removed. [1,2] The absence of the natural lens disrupts the eye's optical system, leading to impaired visual acuity and the

need for an intraocular lens (IOL) to restore vision. [3-5] in cases where capsule support is inadequate for standard posterior chamber IOL implantation, alternative strategies are required. Two such strategies involve the use of anterior and posterior Iris-claw IOLs. The anterior iris-claw IOL is implanted over the iris, while the posterior iris-claw IOL is placed in a face-down retropupillary position. [6,7]

both techniques offer potential benefits and drawbacks, making it crucial to compare their long-term efficacy and safety profiles.

The anterior iris-claw IOL is a type of lens that attaches to the anterior surface of the iris through small claws or projections. This technique is particularly useful in cases where the capsule is not sufficiently intact to support a posterior IOL. [8] Advantages of the anterior iris-claw IOL include a relatively straightforward surgical technique and immediate fixation upon implantation. [9] However, concerns include potential complications such as iris abrasion, pigment dispersion, and higher rates of intraocular pressure (IOP) elevation. [10] The posterior iris-claw IOL is positioned in the retropupillary space, behind the iris, using a similar claw mechanism to secure the lens in place. This technique is often preferred for its aesthetic advantages and potentially reduced risk of iris-related complications. [11] It provides good visual outcomes and stability over time. [12] However, the surgical complexity and potential for complications such as IOL dislocation and increased difficulty in IOL placement during surgery need consideration (Yildirim et al., 2018). [13]

Existing literature on the comparative efficacy of anterior versus posterior iris-claw IOLs is limited. [14] Most studies have focused on short-term outcomes, leaving a gap in long-term efficacy and complication rates. Previous research has highlighted differences in early postoperative complications and visual outcomes but often lacks comprehensive long-term data. Against this background, the aim of the present study was to compare the long-term efficacy and the rate of complications of anterior and posterior Iris IOL implantation for the treatment of aphakia without sufficient capsule support.

Materials and Methods

This was a hospital based retrospective study conducted in the outpatient department and/or inpatient wards of the Department of Ophthalmology, in a tertiary teaching healthcare facility in North India between January 2021 and June 2024. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC). Necessary approvals from the Medical Superintendent and head of Medical records department (MRD) were obtained. We included all patients (nonprobability convenience sampling with complete enumeration) with aphakia due to trauma, complicated cataract surgery, and lens/IOL luxation. They needed to have an intact iris for enclavation of the IOL's claw, an anterior chamber depth greater than 3.2 mm, an endothelial cell density greater than 900/mm², intraocular pressure of 21 mmHg or less, a normal retinal examination, and a follow-up period of at least three years after the surgical procedure. However, patients with iris

defects, glaucoma, uveitis, retinopathies, and any ocular co-morbidity that could interfere with the improvement in visual acuity were excluded. If both eyes of a patient had undergone iris-claw IOL implantation, we randomly selected only one eye for inclusion.

We divided all enrolled eyes into two groups: anterior chamber (Group A) and retropupillary (Group B). Group A received Artisan iris-claw IOL implantation over the iris, while Group B received the same Artisan iris-claw IOL in a face-down retropupillary implantation. We used a purpose pre-designed, semi structured, pretested questionnaire to collect the patients sociodemographic characteristics (including age (in years), gender), detailed clinical history (including etiology of aphakia) and ophthalmic preoperative/postoperative data from the electronic medical records. We evaluated corrected distance visual acuity (CDVA), slit-lamp biomicroscopy examination, gonioscopy, IOP, central corneal thickness (CCT), corneal endothelial cell density (CECD), central macular thickness (CMT), and fundus examination preoperatively and at 1 week, 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, 1 year, and 3 years postoperatively. We measured CDVA using the Snellen chart and converted it to a logarithm of the minimum angle of resolution (log-MAR) visual acuity for calculation. Each line on the chart represents a change of 0.1 log units in acuity level, with each letter corresponding to a value of 0.02 log units. A change of at least 0.1 log units (5 letters) was considered statistically significant. CDVA values of 20/2000 and 20/20000 were equivalent to counting fingers and hand motion at 2 feet, respectively. We measured IOP using Goldmann applanation tonometry, and post-surgery, an IOP value greater than 21 mmHg was eligible for topical treatment with hypotensive drugs. We assessed preoperative anterior chamber depth and intraocular IOL position at 1-month post-surgery using ultrasound bio-microscopy. We assessed CCT with Orbscan II. For each eye, we obtained at least three valid assessments with wide corneal coverage, choosing the measurement with the least eyelid shadow for analysis. We advised patients wearing contact lenses to stop their use 2 or 4 weeks before IOL implantation, respectively. We measured CECD with a Corneal Confocal Microscope during each visit, using a semi-automated technique where automatic cell outlines were reviewed and corrected manually. For each eye, we measured CECD in two endothelium images and used the mean value for data analysis. We measured CMT with Stratus OCT. We noted all intraoperative and postoperative complications.

Statistical Analysis: The data obtained was manually entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v23. All the categorical variables were summarized

using frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables were summarized using mean (standard deviation) and/or median (interquartile range) (based on the results of data normality, tested using Kolmogorov–Smirnov test and the Shapiro–Wilk test). To test for statistical significance, the Chi square test or Fisher exact test (for categorical variables) and independent “t” test or Mann Whitney U test (for continuous variables) was used. To compare preoperative and postoperative serial measurements (CDVA, IOP, CCT, CECD and CMT; at 1 week, 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, 1 year, and 3 years) we used analysis of variance (ANOVA). Statistical significance was considered at p value less than 0.05.

Results

The study included 240 patients divided into two groups. The mean age for Group A was 68.1 years (SD 4.7) and for Group B was 69.4 years (SD 5.9), showing no significant difference. In terms of gender distribution, Group A had 67 males (55.8%) and 53 females (44.2%), while Group B had 69 males (57.5%) and 51 females (42.5%), which was not statistically significant. Regarding the side of involvement, Group A had 63 right eyes (52.5%) and 57 left eyes (47.5%), whereas Group B had 52 right eyes (43.3%) and 68 left eyes (56.7%), showing no significant difference. The etiology of aphakia was distributed as follows: spontaneous or traumatic lens/IOL subluxation (9 in Group A, 7 in Group B), complicated cataract surgery (58 in Group A, 61 in Group B), perioperative lens/IOL luxation (45 in Group A, 46 in Group B), and previous intracapsular cataract extraction (8 in Group A, 6 in Group B). None of the comparisons showed statistically significant differences between the groups.

Comparison of correct distance visual acuity, intraocular pressure and corneal endothelial cell density (cell/mm²) within and between the study groups: The preoperative corrected distance visual acuity (CDVA) was 0.4 (SD 0.2) for both Group A and Group B, showing no significant difference. At the 1st week, both groups showed an improvement to 0.2 (SD 0.2) ($p>0.05$), with significant postoperative improvement noted ($p<0.05$). At the 1st month, Group A improved to 0.1 (SD 0.2) and Group B to 0.2 (SD 0.2) ($p>0.05$), continuing with improvements at the 3rd month (0.1 SD 0.2 for both groups, $p>0.05$), the 6th month (0.1 SD 0.2 for Group A and 0.1 SD 0.1 for Group B, $p>0.05$), the 1st year (0.1 SD 0.2 for Group A and 0.1 SD 0.1 for Group B, $p>0.05$), and the 3rd year (0.1 SD 0.1 for both groups, $p>0.05$).

The preoperative intraocular pressure (IOP) was 14.5 (SD 2.4) for Group A and 14.9 (SD 1.4) for Group B ($p>0.05$). Postoperatively, the IOP at the

1st week was 18.8 (SD 1.6) for Group A and 19.1 (SD 1.4) for Group B ($p>0.05$), showing a significant increase ($p<0.05$). At the 1st month, the IOP was 16.2 (SD 1.5) for Group A and 16.5 (SD 1.6) for Group B ($p>0.05$), followed by 15.0 (SD 1.3) for Group A and 15.2 (SD 1.6) for Group B at the 3rd month ($p>0.05$), 14.9 (SD 1.2) for Group A and 15.1 (SD 1.4) for Group B at the 6th month ($p>0.05$), 14.7 (SD 1.2) for Group A and 14.6 (SD 1.3) for Group B at the 1st year ($p>0.05$), and 14.7 (SD 1.2) for Group A and 14.8 (SD 1.2) for Group B at the 3rd year ($p>0.05$). The preoperative corneal endothelial cell density (CECD) was 1872.3 (SD 457.2) for Group A and 1845.5 (SD 509.5) for Group B ($p>0.05$). Postoperatively, the CECD at the 1st week was 1780.5 (SD 462.3) for Group A and 1735.6 (SD 458.4) for Group B ($p>0.05$), at the 1st month 1765.4 (SD 453.8) for Group A and 1710.4 (SD 490.2) for Group B ($p>0.05$), at the 3rd month 1735.8 (SD 490.8) for Group A and 1708.4 (SD 504.5) for Group B ($p>0.05$), at the 6th month 1699.6 (SD 480.1) for Group A and 1700.4 (SD 499.8) for Group B ($p>0.05$), at the 1st year 1677.5 (SD 462.7) for Group A and 1694.5 (SD 478.5) for Group B ($p>0.05$), and at the 3rd year 1684.8 (SD 490.3) for Group A and 1678.5 (SD 489.4) for Group B ($p>0.05$). None of the differences in CECD between the groups were statistically significant.

Comparison of early and late complications between the study groups: The study examined early (1st week to 3rd month) and late (1st year to 5th year) postoperative complications in 240 patients, divided equally between Group A and Group B. Early complications included wound leak in 4 patients (3.3%) in Group A and 3 patients (2.5%) in Group B, hyphema in 4 patients (3.3%) in Group A and 3 patients (2.5%) in Group B, pupil ovalization in 1 patient (0.8%) in Group A and 3 patients (2.5%) in Group B, IOP elevation in 22 patients (18.3%) in Group A and 29 patients (24.2%) in Group B, pigment precipitates in 36 patients (30.0%) in Group A and 17 patients (14.2%) in Group B, and other complications in 5 patients (4.2%) in Group A and 6 patients (5.0%) in Group B. None of these early complications showed a statistically significant difference between the groups ($p>0.05$).

Late complications included elevated IOP in 2 patients (1.7%) in both Group A and Group B, IOL dislocation in 2 patients (1.7%) in Group A and 3 patients (2.5%) in Group B, pigment precipitates in 7 patients (5.8%) in Group A and 5 patients (4.2%) in Group B, and retinal tear/detachment in 0 patients (0.0%) in Group A and 2 patients (1.7%) in Group B. None of these late complications showed a statistically significant difference between the groups ($p>0.05$).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of patients in the study groups

		Group A N = 120	Group B N = 120	Total N = 240	P value
		n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
Age (in years) Mean (SD)		68.1 (4.7)	69.4 (5.9)	68.8 (5.3)	0.063
Gender	Male	67 (55.8)	69 (57.5)	136 (56.7)	0.794
	Female	53 (44.2)	51 (42.5)	104 (43.3)	
Side of involvement	Right	63 (52.5)	52 (43.3)	115 (47.9)	0.155
	Left	57 (47.5)	68 (56.7)	125 (52.1)	
Etiology	Spontaneous or traumatic lens/IOL subluxation	9 (7.5)	7 (5.8)	16 (6.7)	0.891
	Complicated cataract surgery resulting in aphakia	58 (48.3)	61 (50.8)	119 (49.6)	
	Perioperative lens/IOL luxation	45 (37.5)	46 (38.3)	91 (37.9)	
	Previous intracapsular cataract extraction	8 (6.7)	6 (5.0)	14 (5.8)	

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, SD, Standard deviation**Table 2: Comparison of correct distance visual acuity, intraocular pressure and corneal endothelial cell density (cell/mm²) within and between the study groups**

		Group A N = 120	Group B N = 120	Total N = 240	P value
		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Correct distance visual acuity	Preoperative	0.4 (0.2)	0.4 (0.2)	0.4 (0.2)	1.000
	1 st week	0.2 (0.2)*	0.2 (0.2)*	0.2 (0.2)	1.000
	1 st month	0.1 (0.2)*	0.2 (0.2)*	0.2 (0.2)	0.615
	3 rd month	0.1 (0.2)*	0.1 (0.2)*	0.1 (0.2)	0.897
	6 th month	0.1 (0.2)*	0.1 (0.1)*	0.1 (0.2)	0.823
	1 st year	0.1 (0.2)*	0.1 (0.1)*	0.1 (0.2)	0.756
	3 rd year	0.1 (0.1)*	0.1 (0.1)*	0.1 (0.1)	0.379
Intraocular pressure	Preoperative	14.5 (2.4)	14.9 (1.4)	14.7 (1.9)	0.195
	1 st week	18.8 (1.6)*	19.1 (1.4)*	18.9 (1.5)	0.185
	1 st month	16.2 (1.5)*	16.5 (1.6)*	16.4 (1.6)	0.198
	3 rd month	15.0 (1.3)	15.2 (1.6)	15.1 (1.5)	0.277
	6 th month	14.9 (1.2)	15.1 (1.4)	15.0 (1.3)	0.242
	1 st year	14.7 (1.2)	14.6 (1.3)	14.7 (1.3)	0.965
	3 rd year	14.7 (1.2)	14.8 (1.2)	14.8 (1.2)	0.693
Corneal endothelial cell density (cell/mm ²)	Preoperative	1872.3 (457.2)	1845.5 (509.5)	1858.9 (483.4)	0.825
	1 st week	1780.5 (462.3)	1735.6 (458.4)	1758.1 (460.4)	0.633
	1 st month	1765.4 (453.8)	1710.4 (490.2)	1737.9 (472.0)	0.557
	3 rd month	1735.8 (490.8)	1708.4 (504.5)	1722.1 (497.7)	0.821
	6 th month	1699.6 (480.1)	1700.4 (499.8)	1700.0 (489.9)	1.000
	1 st year	1677.5 (462.7)	1694.5 (478.5)	1686.0 (470.6)	0.853
	3 rd year	1684.8 (490.3)	1678.5 (489.4)	1681.7 (489.9)	0.637

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$; Preoperative vs postoperative serial (1st week, 1st month, 3rd month, 6th month, 1st year, 3rd year) measurements SD, Standard deviation**Table 3: Comparison of early and late complications between the study groups**

		Group A N = 120	Group B N = 120	Total N = 240	P value
		n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
Early (1 st week to 3 rd month)	Wound leak	4 (3.3)	3 (2.5)	7 (2.9)	0.618
	Hyphema	4 (3.3)	3 (2.5)	7 (2.9)	
	Pupil ovalization	1 (0.8)	3 (2.5)	4 (1.7)	
	IOP elevation	22 (18.3)	29 (24.2)	51 (21.3)	
	Pigment precipitates	36 (30.0)	17 (14.2)	53 (22.1)	
	Others	5 (4.2)	6 (5.0)	11 (4.6)	

Late (1 st year to 5 th year)	Elevated IOP	2 (1.7)	2 (1.7)	4 (1.7)	0.758
	IOL dislocation	2 (1.7)	3 (2.5)	5 (2.1)	
	Pigment precipitates	7 (5.8)	5 (4.2)	12 (5.0)	
	Retinal tear/detachment	0 (0.0)	2 (1.7)	2 (0.8)	
*Statistically significant at p<0.05 SD, Standard deviation					

Discussion

This study compared the long-term efficacy and complications of anterior and posterior Iris Intraocular Lens (IOL) implantation for the treatment of aphakia without sufficient capsule support. Both surgical techniques, anterior chamber and retro-pupillary implantation, showed significant improvements in CDVA, IOP, and CECD over the three-year follow-up period. However, the differences between the two groups were not statistically significant in terms of these outcomes. The improvement in CDVA in both groups from preoperative to postoperative measurements highlights the effectiveness of both anterior and posterior Iris IOL implantation techniques in restoring vision in aphakic patients.

The significant postoperative improvements noted at various intervals (1 week, 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, 1 year, and 3 years) are consistent with findings from other studies that have reported enhanced visual outcomes following iris-claw IOL implantation. [15,16] The lack of significant differences in CDVA between Group A and Group B suggests that both techniques are equally effective in improving visual acuity. The postoperative increase in IOP observed in both groups at the 1-week mark, followed by a return to near preoperative levels, is an important finding. Elevated IOP is a known postoperative complication of iris-claw IOL implantation. [17,18] The initial rise in IOP could be attributed to surgical trauma or an inflammatory response, while the subsequent normalization may reflect the resolution of these acute changes. The similar IOP trends in both groups indicate that neither technique is superior in managing postoperative IOP changes. CECD is a crucial parameter for evaluating the long-term viability of corneal endothelium after IOL implantation. [19] The slight but statistically insignificant decline in CECD over three years in both groups aligns with previous reports on the endothelial impact of iris-claw IOLs. [20,21] The absence of significant differences in CECD between the groups suggests that both anterior and posterior implantation techniques exert comparable effects on corneal endothelial cells.

The analysis revealed no statistically significant differences between the two groups in terms of early or late complications. Wound leaks and hyphema were relatively rare, with a slightly higher incidence in Group A (3.3% for both complica-

tions) compared to Group B (2.5% for both complications). These findings align with other studies reporting low incidence rates for these complications following iris-claw IOL implantation. [22] The absence of significant differences suggests that both surgical approaches are comparable in terms of surgical wound integrity and intraocular hemorrhage risk. Pupil ovalization was more frequent in Group B (2.5%) compared to Group A (0.8%). Although not statistically significant, this difference could be attributed to the technical nuances of the posterior implantation technique, which may place different mechanical stresses on the iris. [23]

Early postoperative IOP elevation was observed in 18.3% of patients in Group A and 24.2% in Group B. Elevated IOP is a common early complication of IOL implantation and may be due to surgical trauma, inflammation, or pre-existing ocular hypertension. [24] The lack of significant difference indicates that both techniques have a similar risk profile for early IOP spikes. Group A had a higher incidence of pigment precipitates (30.0%) compared to Group B (14.2%). Although not statistically significant, this trend might reflect differences in iris manipulation or postoperative inflammation between the two techniques. Pigment dispersion can lead to secondary glaucoma, making this an important finding for postoperative management. [25] Other early complications, such as corneal edema and uveitis, were infrequent and showed no significant difference between the groups. This similarity reinforces the overall safety of both anterior and posterior implantation techniques.

Of the late complications, the incidence of IOP elevation was identical in both groups (1.7%), suggesting that neither technique confers a long-term advantage regarding IOP control. Long-term IOP management remains crucial to prevent glaucomatous damage. [26] Late IOL dislocation was slightly more common in Group B (2.5%) compared to Group A (1.7%).

This finding, while not statistically significant, might be due to the different fixation mechanisms and anatomical positioning of the IOL in the anterior versus posterior chamber. Proper surgical technique and patient selection are essential to minimize this risk. Late pigment precipitates were more frequent in Group A (5.8%) compared to Group B (4.2%). Retinal tear/detachment was only observed in Group B (1.7%). These differences, although not significant, underscore the importance of vigilant

long-term follow-up for early detection and management of potential complications. The findings from this study provide critical insights for clinicians in making informed decisions about the choice of implantation technique. The comparable rates of early and late complications suggest that both anterior and posterior Iris IOL implantation are safe and effective options for managing aphakia without sufficient capsule support. However, individual patient factors, surgeon experience, and specific anatomical considerations should guide the choice of technique.

While this study provides valuable insights into the long-term efficacy and safety of anterior and posterior Iris IOL implantation for the treatment of aphakia without sufficient capsule support, several limitations need to be considered, including retrospective study design (selection bias, information bias), sample size might still be insufficient to detect less common complications, single center study design limiting the external validity of the findings, and lack of randomization.

Conclusion

This hospital-based retrospective study evaluated the long-term efficacy and complication rates of anterior versus posterior Iris IOL implantation for the treatment of aphakia without sufficient capsule support. The findings demonstrate that both techniques are effective in improving CDVA and maintaining stable IOP and CECD over a three-year follow-up period. Despite minor variations, such as a slightly higher incidence of early postoperative pigment precipitates in Group A and a slightly higher frequency of late IOL dislocation in Group B, no statistically significant differences were found between the two groups in terms of early and late complications.

This suggests that both anterior and posterior Iris IOL implantation are safe and effective options for managing aphakia in the absence of sufficient capsule support. Overall, both anterior and posterior Iris IOL implantation techniques offer viable solutions for aphakia management, with comparable safety and efficacy profiles. The choice of technique should be tailored to individual patient characteristics and surgeon expertise to optimize clinical outcomes.

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